
The Effect of Good Corporate Governance Mechanism on Earnings Management

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) on earnings management. Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is represented by the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners, and the size of the audit committee, while earnings management is measured by discretionary accruals. This study uses a population in the form of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2018 and 2019. The sample was selected by the purposive sampling method. The criteria were manufacturing companies engaged in the consumer good industry sub-sector and produced 84 companies as research samples. The method of testing the hypothesis is done using multiple linear regression. The results of this study indicate that the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent commissioner board and the size of the audit committee have an effect on earnings management.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the theory of the firm, the company has the main objective, namely to maximize the company's wealth or value Salvator (2005), one of the efforts made is to hire a professional to become a manager or a commissioner to manage the company, this is in line with agency theory. According to Boediono (2005) to measure the performance of the management the parameter commonly used is the earnings information contained in the company's comprehensive income / loss statement (Dania et al. 2019).

Agents who run the company certainly have more complete and more information about the internal conditions of the company when compared to the principal or what is commonly known as information asymmetry (Ghozali 2016). According to Herlambang and Darsono Darsono (2015), information asymmetry that occurs

between the principal and the agent can encourage the agent to present information in the financial statements tailored to the interests of the agent towards the principal. Agents can choose to use certain accounting policies that allow agents to regulate earnings (increase or decrease) according to their wishes. This behavior is what we call earnings management (Herlambang and Darsono 2015). We can define earnings management as a process that is carried out deliberately by the agent to produce a profit figure according to his wishes (Irmadariyani et al. 2019).

The worst impact a company will experience from the practice of earnings management is bankruptcy (Eriandani and Winarno 2021). Like the bankruptcy case that occurred at the Enron company (Scoot 2009). Enron's management is doing window dressing on the numbers in its financial statements so that the company performance looks very good (Mudawiyah et al. 2019). The company made a

mark-up on revenues of 600 million US dollars, and hid its debts of 1.2 billion US dollars, while in Indonesia there was a case of earnings management, one of which was at PT Garuda Indonesia Tbk. It is known that at that time Garuda recorded a net profit of 5.018 million US dollars. After management was asked to restate its financial statements, Garuda Indonesia actually recorded a net loss of US \$ 175.028 million, from cases that have occurred related to earnings management indicating that one of the factors causing the practice of earnings management is due to the agent as the company manager want to cover the actual condition of the company to show good performance to the principal (Sulistiyono et al. 2020). So as to minimize the conflict of interest between the agent and the principal which causes earnings management practices, it is necessary here to have good corporate governance (GCG) practices (KNKG 2006). According to the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP) on its official website, GCG is defined as a company control and regulatory system that can be seen from the relationship mechanism between the various parties who manage the company (hard definition), as well as in terms of "values" (commitment, rules of the game) (Agustin et al. 2021). as well as the practice of conducting business in a healthy and ethical manner) contained in the management mechanism itself (soft definition) (Widyaningdyah 2001).

Several previous studies that examined the effect of GCG on earnings management have been carried out. GCG is often represented by the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners, and the size of the audit committee (Gunawan et al. 2015). The results of the research conducted Mahiswari and Nugroho (2014), stated that the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners and the audit committee has no effect on earnings management. The results of this study are contrary to the research conducted Nasution and Setiawan (2007); Jao and Pagalung (2011), the results show that the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners and the audit committee has a negative effect on earnings management (Jao and Pagalung 2011).

Based on the explanation of this phenomenon and also the results of previous research which show different results, the author is

interested in examining the effect of GCG on earnings management in manufacturing companies in the consumer good industry sub-sector listed on the IDX in 2018-2019, the authors use board size, composition independent board of commissioners, and audit committee size as independent variables (Jensen and Meckling 1976).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Agency Theory

Agency theory (agency theory) was first put forward by Jensen and Meckling (1976), this agency theory explains the relationship between the principal and the agent, a relationship is said to be an agency if the owner and / or shareholder as principal employs another person, namely an agent to provide a service in the form of managing company resources and also delegating authority in decision making to the agent (Ujjiyantho and Pramuka 2007).

Agency theory is closely related to information asymmetry, which will later become one of the obstacles that will be faced in the principal and agent relationship (Adita et al. 2021). Information asymmetry is a condition that shows the imbalance of information held between the principal and agent (Liyundira et al. 2021). The principal only has information disclosed by the agent, while the agent as the party who runs the company certainly has more complete and more information about the internal conditions of the company than the principal (Widyaningdyah 2001). Information asymmetry can be a motivation for the agent to hide some information that is not known to the principal (Kustono 2020). So that the information reported does not show the real information in order to maximize profits for the agent (Ujjiyantho and Pramuka 2007).

Earnings Management

Earnings management can be interpreted as an activity that is carried out deliberately by an agent to generate profit figures that match his wishes (Nasution and Setiawan 2007). Gunawan et al. (2015) also defines earnings management as a condition in which agents intervene in the process of preparing financial statements. So that they can smooth, increase and decrease earnings (Febryanti et al. 2017). Earnings management can also reduce the level of credibility of the financial statements that are prepared, and can also increase bias and can disturb users of

financial statements who believe that agent-engineered profits are profits without any manipulation and ultimately cause the decisions taken to be wrong (Ujiyantho and Pramuka 2007).

Earnings management actions can be motivated by several things. Scoot (2009) argued that there are six factors that can motivate agents to practice earnings management, namely because of the bonus plan that will be given if company profits increase, the existence of long-term debt contracts, political motivation, tax motivation, CEO change, and bidding initial stock (Mahiswari and Nugroho 2014).

Good Corporate Governance (GCG)

We can define GCG as a set of rules governing relationships with all external and internal parties relating to the rights and obligations of each party (Kustono 2021). Meanwhile, according to the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP) on its official website, GCG is defined as a company control and regulatory system that can be seen from the mechanism of the relationship between the various parties who manage the company (hard definition), as well as in terms of "values" (commitments, rules play, as well as the practice of conducting business in a healthy and ethical manner) contained in the management mechanism itself (soft definition) (Kuncorowati et al. 2021). The main key to the success of GCG is to build a good monitoring and control system (Herlambang and Darsono Darsono 2015).

National Committee on Governance Policy KNKG (2006), states that each company has an obligation to ensure that all GCG principles have been applied to every line and aspect of the company's business (Novitasari et al. 2019). There are five principles of GCG, namely transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence and fairness (Boediono 2005). The elements used to measure GCG in this study are the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners and the audit committee (Aduroh and Paramu 2021).

The thinking framework in this study can be described in the following figure:

Figure 1. Framework of thinking

Source: Compiled by researcher, 2020

Effect of Board of Commissioners Size on Earnings Management

In a company, the board of commissioners plays a major role in the company's management process and has a very important role in the process of implementing GCG (Wijaya et al. 2021). The board of commissioners is given the task and responsibility to supervise and also provide advice to the board of directors and ensure that the company has implemented GCG in all lines and business aspects of the company (Salvator 2005). Supervision from the board of commissioners is very important given the conflict of interest that motivates the agent to carry out earnings management which will reduce the level of credibility of information so that it has an impact on decreasing investor confidence which will harm the principal (Dania et al. 2019). So that to carry out its duties as supervisor, the board of commissioners is given access to internal company information. According to KNKG (2006), determining the size of the board of commissioners in a company must consider the level of complexity of the company.

Several previous studies have been carried out, and the results are very mixed (Djaya Atmadja et al. 2019). Research conducted Nasution and Setiawan (2007); Jao and Pagalung (2011) concluded that the size of the board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management, so based on this the authors formulate the following hypothesis:

H₁: The size of the Board of Commissioners has an effect on earnings management.

The Effect of the Composition of the Independent Board of Commissioners on Earnings Management

The composition of the independent board of commissioners plays an important role in the process of implementing GCG, because supervision of the company will be more effective with the presence of an independent board of commissioners without any intervention from

management because independent commissioners are free from influence from any party (Paramita et al. 2020). So that it is expected to reduce earnings management, it can be concluded that The minimal number of independent board of commissioners can make agents more flexible to intervene in financial reports as desired, so that an appropriate and adequate composition of independent board of commissioners is needed to reduce earnings management practices and the successful implementation of GCG (Park 2017).

Several previous studies have been carried out, and the results are very mixed. Research results from Nasution and Setiawan (2007); Jao and Pagalung (2011); Herlambang and Darsono (2015) concluded that the composition of the independent board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management. Based on this, the authors formulate the following hypothesis:

H₂: The composition of the Independent Commissioner has an effect on Earning Management

The Effect of the Audit Committee on Earnings Management

The audit committee has a very important role in inhibiting practical earnings management by the agent (As sajjad et al. 2021). The audit committee is also expected to carry out practices that are contrary to GCG from an early age (Arif and Putra 2022). The minimum number of audit committees consists of three (3) people, the members of the audit committee who come from the independent board of commissioners only consist of one (1) person while the rest are from external independent parties (Sri Kustono and Adi Nanggala 2019).

Several previous studies have been carried out, and the results are very mixed. Research conducted Nasution and Setiawan (2007); Jao and Pagalung 2011) concluded that the audit committee has an effect on earnings management, based on this, the authors formulate the following hypothesis:

H₃: The Audit Committee has an effect on Earning Management.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Types and Sources of Data

The type of data that the author uses in this study is secondary data (data obtained indirectly) in the form of annual financial

reports for the period 2018-2019, which were obtained from www.idx.co.id.

Population and Sample

The population used by the author in this study are manufacturing companies listed on the IDX for the period 2018-2019, the reason for selecting the population is because manufacturing companies are considered the most sensitive to economic changes. The research sample was taken using the purposive sampling method, namely the determination of a random sample based on the suitability of certain characteristics and criteria, the criteria were manufacturing companies engaged in the consumer good industry sub-sector.

Operational Definition of Variables

Independent Variable

The independent variable used by the author in this study is GCG which is then represented by the size of the board of commissioners, composition of the independent commissioner board, and the size of the audit committee (Sumani et al. 2020). The independent variables of this study are measured in the following way:

1. The size of the board of commissioners is measured based on the total number of commissioners from the sample companies;
2. The composition of the independent board of commissioners, measured based on the percentage of the number of independent commissioners to the total number of commissioners of the sample companies;
3. The size of the audit committee, measured based on the total number of audit committees of the sample companies.

Dependent Variables

The dependent variable used by the author in this study is earnings management as measured by discretionary accruals (Sumani et al. 2021). Discretionary accruals are a way to reduce earnings reporting that are difficult to detect through manipulation of accounting policies related to accruals (Sumani and Roziq 2020). This study measures discretionary accruals using the Modified Jones Model with the calculation formula, as follows:

$$TA_t = \alpha_1(1/A_{t-1}) + \alpha_2(\Delta REV_t - \Delta REC_t) + \alpha_3(PPE_t) + \varepsilon_t$$

Figure 2. Calculation Formula

Where:

- TA_t =Total Accruals in year t
- A_{t-1} =Total assets in year t-1
- ΔREV_t =The difference between the company's revenue in year t and t-1
- PPE_t =Value of Property, Plant, and Equipment in year t
- ΔREC_t =Value of net receivables received through the difference between years t and t-1

Methods of Data Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics are not used to test hypotheses, but are only used to clarify the circumstances or characteristics of the data used in this study.

Classic Assumption Test

The data analysis method used to test the hypothesis in this study uses multiple regression model, before conducting the regression test, the data used must meet the classical assumption test. The classical assumption test referred to consists of the normality test, multicollinearity test, autocorrelation test and heteroscedasticity test.

Hypothesis Testing

The data analysis method used to test the hypothesis in this study uses multiple regression models, regression test is used to test the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Researchers used SPSS version 23 software to perform statistical tests.

Determination Coefficient Test (R²)

According to Ghazali (2016) R² used to measure how much the model's ability to explain variations in the dependent variable, R² has a weakness, namely bias towards the number of independent variables used in the model, meaning that every additional one variable, then the R² value will increase without considering the possibility that the independent variable has no effect on the variable dependent, so that many believe to use the adjusted R² value when making decisions.

Simultaneous Significance Test (Test F)

According to Ghazali (2016) F test is useful to show whether all the independent variables used in this study simultaneously affect the dependent variable.

Test of Significance of Individual Parameters (t Test)

According to Ghazali (2016) t statistical test is useful for showing how much influence each independent variable individually has in explaining the dependent variable.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Sample Description

The data obtained by the author from www.idx.co.id in the 2018-2019 period, there were 63 companies with details that can be seen as follows:

Table 1. List of Research Sample

Information	2018	2019	Total
Manufacturing Companies (Consumer Good Industry) Listed On The IDX	63	63	126
The Company Does Not Issue Fin.Sta Year 2017, 2018 & 2019	(14)	(14)	(28)
Sample	49	49	98
Outliers	(4)	(5)	(9)
Elimination Log Results	(2)	(3)	(5)
The Sample Used	43	41	84

Source: Secondary Data Processed By The Author, 2020

The results of the descriptive statistical test of each variable used in the study can be seen as follows:

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Log_X1	89	,30	,85	,5360	,01461	,13780
Log_X2	89	1,40	2,00	1,6249	,01317	,12427
Log_X3	89	,30	,60	,4681	,00518	,04885
Log_Y	84	8,90	11,89	10,5643	,08094	,74182
Valid N (listwise)	84					

Figure 3. Descriptive Statistical Test

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Discussion of Statistical Test Results

The test results of the classical assumption test consisting of normality test, multicollinearity test, autocorrelation test, and heteroscedasticity test are as follows:

Normality Test

The data normality test was done by using the P-Plot test, but if you are still in doubt

you can use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov non-parametric statistical test. The author chooses to use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov because the test results are in the form of an exact number, while the P-Plot is an image that each person might see differently, sometimes by looking at the P-Plot image the data looks normal but after the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test it turns out that the data abnormal. Figure 4 shows the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		84
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	,60926137
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,060
	Positive	,058
	Negative	-,060
Test Statistic		,060
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}

Figure 4. The Result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results show the Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.200 and greater than 0.05, meaning that the regression model meets the requirements of the normality test.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test results show that all tolerance values are greater than 0.100 and all VIF values are less than 10.00 means that the regression model is free from multicollinearity symptoms, so the research data is suitable for use in the regression model.

Collinearity Statistics	
Tolerance	VIF
,932	1,073
,943	1,060
,943	1,061

Figure 5. The Result of Multicollinearity Test
Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Autocorrelation Test

The autocorrelation test is carried out using the Durbin Watson statistical test, if the Durbin Watson value lies between du to (4-du) it means that there are no autocorrelation symptoms. The results of the Durbin Watson test showed a value of 1.967, with K (3) and N (84)

and with a significance of 5%. This value is between du (1.7462) and 4-du (2.2538), meaning that the regression model does not have autocorrelation problems.

Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
,300	,62058	1,967

Figure 6. The Result of Durbin Watson Statistical Test

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test uses the Scatterplot statistical test, there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity because the dots are spread out and do not form a clear pattern.

Figure 7. The Result of Scatterplot Statistical Test

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The results of statistical tests show the adjusted R Square value of 0.300, meaning that 30% of earnings management can be explained by the independent variable.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,570 ^a	,325	,300	,62058	1,967

Figure 8. The Result of The Coefficient Determination

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Simultaneous Significance Test (Uji F)

The results of the F test show a significance level of 0.000 and less than 0.05, meaning that the independent variable can simultaneously influence the dependent variable, namely earnings management.

F	Sig.
12,866	,000 ^b

Figure 9. Simultaneous Significance Test Result

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Test of Significance of Individual Parameters (t test)

The t test results show that all significance values of each variable are less than 0.05, meaning that all independent variables have an effect on the dependent variable with a confidence level of 95%.

t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
4,633	,000		
4,034	,000	,932	1,073
2,328	,022	,943	1,060
2,989	,004	,943	1,061

Figure 10. The Result of Test of Significance of Individual Parameters

Source: Secondary Data Processed By SPSS, 2020

Discussion of Research Results

Effect of Board of Commissioners Size on Earnings Management

Based on the regression test that has been carried out, it is obtained t count of 4.034 with a significance level of 0.000. The significance value is smaller than 0.05, this indicates that the size of the board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management, and it means that H₁ is accepted (Danar PARAMITA et al. 2020). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted Jao and Pagalung (2011) who concluded that the size of the board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management. However, these results are contrary to the research conducted Gulzar and Zongjun (2011); Herlambang and Darsono Darsono (2015) who concluded that the size of the board

of commissioners has no effect on earnings management.

The Effect of the Composition of the Independent Board of Commissioners on Earnings Management

Based on the regression test that has been carried out, it is obtained t count of 2.328 with a significance level of 0.022. The significance value is smaller than 0.05, this indicates that the size of the board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management, and it means that H₂ is accepted. The results of this study are in line with the research conducted Jao and Pagalung (2011); Herlambang and Darsono (2015) concluded that the composition of the independent board of commissioners has an effect on earnings management. However, these results are contrary to the research conducted Gulzar and Zongjun (2011) who concluded that the composition of the independent board of commissioners has no effect on earnings management.

The Effect of the Audit Committee on Earnings Management

Based on the regression test that has been done, it is obtained t count of 2.989 with a significance level of 0.004. The significance value is smaller than 0.05, this indicates that the size of the audit committee has an effect on earnings management, and it means that H₃ is accepted (Kustono et al. 2021). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted Jao and Pagalung (2011) who concluded that the size of the audit committee has an effect on earnings management. However, these results are contrary to the research conducted Herlambang and Darsono (2015); Gulzar and Zongjun (2011) who concluded that the size of the audit committee has no effect on earnings management.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

The regression test results show that the size of the board of commissioners, the composition of the independent board of commissioners, and the size of the audit committee have an effect on earnings management, which means that the presence of the board of commissioners, the independent board of commissioners, and the audit committee has an effect on earnings management practices by management.

This research is expected to be able to provide additional knowledge and understanding

related to the effect of good corporate governance mechanisms on earnings management in manufacturing companies engaged in the consumer good industry sub-sector, which can later be used by the principal of the related companies and academics.

This study has several limitations, first, apart from the independent variables used by the author in this study, there are still many independent variables that can represent GCG so that there are many other factors that can affect earnings management, secondly the time series for dependent variable data is relatively short, and There are quite a lot of excluded from the research sample so that it is relatively influential on the research results. Based on these limitations, it is hoped that further research can use other independent variables, as well as a relatively longer time series in estimating earnings management, using other measurement methods for earnings management and also using sub-sector companies other than those used by the author in the study.

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